

Segmentation techniques for Arabic handwritten: a review

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ABSTRACT

Image segmentation refers to the process of partitioning a page into distinct sections. This technique aims to improve and transform the image's representation into a more coherent and user-friendly format. Its common application involves identifying objects and boundaries (such as lines and curves) within images. However, this paper focuses on discussing segmentation methods specifically tailored for Arabic handwritten content. Dealing with the segmentation of Arabic handwritten material poses a significant challenge due to the diverse handwriting styles and the interconnection between Arabic letters. The paper will also touch on the classification of segmentation algorithms originally designed for modern documents, illustrating their adaptation in document processing. Furthermore, the paper will address the difficulties associated with segmenting Arabic handwritten content, including variations in writing style, the connected nature of Arabic characters, the complexity of Arabic cursive writing and as well as the diacritics challenges. Lastly, a concise overview of previously widely used segmentation techniques in various research endeavors will be provided.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Image segmentation is a process where features with similar attributes are identified and grouped together. This procedure can involve statistical clustering, thresholding, edge detection, region identification, or a combination of these methods. Segmentation is typically a fundamental step in image analysis, marking the transition from treating individual pixels as the units of perception to dealing with coherent objects within the image that consist of multiple pixels. Furthermore, the segmentation phase holds significance because it impacts the accuracy of recognition and the origin of errors in recognition [1]. When segmentation is executed effectively, all subsequent stages of image analysis become more straightforward and uncomplicated. Image segmentation serves as a crucial and complex operation in image processing. The techniques employed in image segmentation aim to partition an image into coherent portions that exhibit similar characteristics, as shown in Figure 1.

The objective of segmentation is to streamline the representation of an image into a meaningful and analyzable format. In the field of image analysis, segmentation is the initial step [2]. It encompasses the division of an image into contiguous and meaningful segments or regions. Segmentation stands as a pivotal first phase for a variety of image analysis methodologies. The outcome of image segmentation in terms of its

accuracy and nature significantly influences the performance of these image analysis techniques [3]. This paper is dedicated to exploring segmentation techniques specific to Arabic handwritten documents. While Arabic characters serve as scripts for languages like Arabic, Uygur, Urdu, and Farsi, they have not gained as much attention in character recognition as Chinese or Latin characters have. Despite being more challenging due to their diverse forms, Arabic characters hold interest for researchers, particularly in the realm of automatically recognizing handwritten characters [4].

Figure 1. Example of image segmentation in Arabic handwritten word

2. BACKGROUND

There exist multiple approaches utilized for image segmentation, each with its own significance. Prominent segmentation techniques commonly employed encompass thresholding, edge detection, region-based, clustering, watershed, partial differential equation (PDE), and artificial neural network (ANN) methods, as illustrated in Figure 2. These techniques differ in their segmentation methods [5].

Figure 2. Classification of image segmentation techniques

2.1. Thresholding method

This method represents the most straightforward and uncomplicated approach to image segmentation. It distinguishes image pixels based on their intensity level. This method is suitable for images where foreground elements are lighter than the background. Moreover, there are three categories of thresholding: global thresholding, variable thresholding, and diverse thresholding. Furthermore, these three fundamental types of thresholding include [6], [7]:

- Global thresholding: Employs a consistent threshold value (T) for the entire image.
- Variable thresholding: Adapts threshold value (T) across the image.
- Multiple thresholding: Utilizes multiple threshold values, like T_0 and T_1 , determined via image histograms.

2.2. Edge based segmentation method

The edge-based segmentation techniques stand as well-established methods within image processing in their own right. These segmentation approaches, relying on rapid shifts in intensity values within an image, find their foundation in the fact that a sole intensity value does not adequately convey edge information. Two fundamental edge-based segmentation methods include gray histograms and gradient-based methods. To identify edges, basic edge detection techniques like Sobel, Canny, and Robert's operators can be employed. The result of these techniques yields a binary image essentially. These methods are grounded in structural techniques hinging on cut-off detection [8].

2.3. Region based segmentation method

The region-based segmentation method involves dividing the page into distinct regions sharing similar characteristics. It is a method for directly determining the region by iteratively encompassing neighboring pixels that share similarities and are connected to the seed pixel. Moreover, this approach encompasses a greater number of pixels to acquire additional information for characterizing the region. This method comprises two primary techniques [9]–[11]:

- a. Region growing method: This method segments the image into various sections based on the expansion from seed pixels. These seeds can be manually assigned using prior knowledge or automatically designated according to specific applications.
- b. Region splitting and merging method: This approach employs two fundamental techniques, splitting and merging, to divide the image into discrete areas. Region splitting involves iteratively separating image regions with similar attributes, while region merging combines neighboring comparable regions.

2.4. Clustering based segmentation method

The clustering-based segmentation technique involves dividing the image into clusters that contain pixels with similar attributes. Data clustering is a process that groups data elements into clusters, ensuring that elements within the same cluster are more similar to each other than to elements in other clusters. Two fundamental types of clustering exist [12], [13]:

- a. Hard clustering: This method separates the image into a defined set of clusters, such that each pixel belongs to only one cluster. In other words, each pixel is exclusively assigned to a single cluster.
- b. Soft clustering: This type of clustering is more organic, as strict separation is less likely due to the presence of noise. Soft clustering techniques are particularly useful for image segmentation scenarios where a clear division is not feasible. Thus, this technique offers greater flexibility compared to other methods [12].

2.5. Watershed based methods

The commonly employed watershed-based method utilizes the concept of topological transformation. In this approach, intensity levels correspond to bowls formed at their minima points, from which water spills. As water reaches the rim of a bowl, adjacent bowls are amalgamated. The watershed method views the image's gradient as a topographic surface, designating pixels with steeper gradients as continuous boundaries [14].

2.6. PDE based method

The segmentation techniques based on PDE are rapid methods suitable for time-sensitive applications. Two key PDE techniques are noteworthy: the non-linear isotropic diffusion filter, enhancing edges, and the curved non-quadratic variation restoration filter, eliminating noise. The outcomes of the PDE technique result in blurred edges and boundaries that can be adjusted using nearby operators. The fourth-order PDE method is employed to diminish image noise, while the second-order PDE technique is used for more accurate edge and boundary detection [12].

2.7. Ann based method

Artificial neural network-based segmentation techniques replicate the learning processes of the human brain to achieve decision-making objectives. Currently, this method is widely employed for segmenting medical images, effectively isolating the desired image from its background. A neural network comprises numerous interconnected nodes, with each connection assigned a specific weight. This approach operates independently of PDE. The problem is converted into challenges that are addressed by the neural network. This technique comprises two fundamental stages: feature extraction and segmentation using the neural network [10].

3. RELATED WORK

In this section, it is explained the related work for Arabic handwritten segmentation starting from categorization of existing segmentation algorithms which we compare the capability of each technique, we also come across the challenges of Arabic handwritten segmentation. Furthermore, diacritics segmentation for Arabic handwritten document is discussed. Finally, a summary of the latest segmentation techniques that are used in this field is elaborated.

3.1. Categorization of present segmentation methods

Numerous methodologies for image segmentation have been proposed, each with distinct characteristics. However, these methods can be classified based on the anticipated outcomes of the corresponding image segmentation algorithms. Noteworthy segmentation algorithms include: X–Y cuts or projection profiles, the run length smoothing algorithm (RLSA), document spectrum analysis, whitespace assessment, constrained text lines [15], the Hough transform used for skew detection and correction in mushaf, line detection within the image space [16], Voronoi tessellation, and scale space analysis. An experiment by Shiekh *et al.* [17] employed a region-based technique for diacritics segmentation and produced a promising result. The Watershed transform, which represents ridges dividing areas drained by distinct river systems [18], is instrumental in defining boundaries for image region separation [19], also aiding in detecting non-linear spacing between characters [20]. Contour tracing initiates from a source point and traces the character boundary to the point of contact [21]. It is important to note that the majority of the aforementioned segmentation algorithms are primarily tailored for existing documents. Table 1 outlines and illustrates how these algorithms are utilized in image preprocessing. Additionally, a comparison of various segmentation techniques is presented in Table 1, building upon the groundwork of [15]. We have contributed to this table, particularly focusing on the last three sections: region-based, watershed transform, contour tracing.

Table 1. Classification of existing segmentation methods

Segmentation algorithms	Printed document	Hand-written documents	Historical documents	Existing research				
				Page segmentation	Text line segmentation	Word segmentation	Character segmentation	Diacritic segmentation
X-Y cuts	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	
RLSA	√	√	√	√	√	√		
Docstrum	√			√	√			
Whitespace analysis	√			√	√			
Constrained text line	√			√	√			
Hough transform	√			√	√		√	
Voronoi	√			√	√			
Scale space analysis	√	√	√	√	√	√		
Region-based		√						√
Watershed transform		√			√		√	
Contour traced		√		√	√		√	

3.2. Challenges of Arabic handwritten segmentation techniques

The Arabic language, with its rich history and extensive vocabulary, has remained largely unchanged for a significant duration. However, due to its widespread usage, it is considered linguistically abundant. The challenge of segmenting Arabic handwritten text is huge, due to diverse handwriting styles and the intricate connections between Arabic letters. Despite this, a reliable solution to this challenging issue has yet to emerge [22]. Additionally, even though handwritten text varies from person to person, the segmentation of such text into words, lines, and characters remains a complex endeavor [23]. Handling non-Latin scripts like Arabic presents even greater challenges; aside from writing variations, the presence of diacritical marks and the abundance of ascender and descender characters further complicate the segmentation process. To address this intricacy and leverage it as an advantage, especially considering Arabic's semi-cursive nature, it is imperative to develop robust segmentation techniques specific to Arabic handwritten content. These techniques should address the difficulties by reviewing existing segmentation methods suitable for Arabic handwritten documents [24]. Consequently, numerous researchers are actively seeking solutions to this issue, achieving commendable progress; however, further research is warranted to enhance the existing approaches to segmenting Arabic handwritten content.

3.2.1. Diacritic segmentation for Arabic handwritten

Undoubtedly, diacritics hold significant importance in the Arabic language, and they can be added to letters in various positions, such as above or below the letter. In traditional Arabic writing, native speakers often do not rely heavily on diacritics, as they can comprehend the meaning from the context of the sentence. However, for non-native Arabic readers, the absence of diacritics can pose challenges in grasping word meanings, potentially leading to misinterpretation of the text. Nonetheless, from a technical standpoint, these diacritics also complicate the segmentation process due to their challenging detection. As a result, many research papers consider diacritics as noise or unnecessary features in the context of image processing for Arabic handwritten content. Consequently, diacritics are not extensively emphasized in studies of this nature.

A study carried out by *et al.* [17] undertook an experiment to extract diacritics from handwritten images using a region-based approach. The researcher's methodology involved, first, capturing the connected components within a binary image. Subsequently, they assessed the characteristics of image regions essentially, measuring the properties of each connected component within the binary image. Given the relatively small size of diacritics, the researcher determined the thresholding properties of region area based on measurements of low area [25]. This implies that smaller regional areas correspond to smaller objects, specifically diacritics in this case. Conversely, larger region areas correspond to more significant objects, such as primary elements like words and characters. The result of this experiment is presented in Figures 3 and 4. Figure 3 represents the binary image that will be used to extract diacritics features from, while Figure 4 presents the outcome of the study which is extracted diacritics objects which are in other sense called secondary objects. The main reason for conducting this study is to clarify that diacritics objects in Arabic handwritten are of a paramount importance and removing them from the image could lead to losing some important features for recognizing the document originality in Arabic handwritten [17].

Figure 3. Primary objects

Figure 4. Secondary objects (diacritics)

3.2.2. Summary of previous segmentation techniques for Arabic handwritten document

Numerous segmentation methods for Arabic handwritten documents have gained significant traction in various research endeavors. Despite the absence of a dependable technique for segmenting Arabic handwritten document and the challenges posed by the diverse styles of handwriting, we have undertaken a concise literature review of past segmentation techniques specific to Arabic handwritten documents, as shown in Table 2 (see in appendix). These techniques serve multiple purposes in relation to segmenting Arabic handwritten documents, aiming to contribute to effective image processing solutions.

4. CONCLUSION

This article delves into a range of topics concerning techniques for image segmentation. The paper undertook a classification of image segmentation algorithms primarily designed for modern documents, aiming to elucidate how these algorithms are applied in document processing. Additionally, the challenges posed by segmentation techniques for Arabic handwritten content were addressed, stemming from variations in writing style, the interconnectedness of Arabic characters, and strategies to manage the intricacies of Arabic cursive writing. Furthermore, the methods employed in segmenting Arabic script were explained, providing insight into their accuracy and average performance rates. To conclude, a comprehensive overview

of previously widely employed segmentation techniques for Arabic handwritten documents was presented. In the future, there are plans to conduct further reviews of segmentation techniques specific to Arabic handwritten content, with the aim of identifying robust methods that align with the objectives of this research.

APPENDIX

Table 2. Summary of previous segmentation techniques for Arabic handwritten

Ref.	Year	Method/Technique	Datasets	Findings
[26]	2019	seam carving	Public database, Arabic handwritten documents	It demonstrated a line detection accuracy of 97.5% at a matching score of 90%. This technique can be utilized across diverse writing styles, including both printed and handwritten forms.
[27]	2021	Machine learning	Randomly selected images with different angles from Arabic handwritten documents	The segmentation approach put forth attained an impressive accuracy rate of 98.18%. Moreover, the suggested method holds potential for expansion into a novel application, capable of being employed for recognizing Arabic handwritten text without concern for its logical or sentence structure.
[28]	2019	Novel algorithm	IFN/ENIT: database of handwritten Tunisian town names, and AHDB: a database for Arabic word spotting and recognition	It exhibits high accuracy levels with exceptional efficiency by mitigating the issue of excessive segmentation, which arises from open character segmentation, and by adapting the segmentation in scenarios involving character adjacency or inaccuracies in word image segmentation.
[29]	2019	Hough transform	IFN/ENIT and Agriculture and Horticulture Development Board (AHDB)	The effectiveness of the suggested method's performance hinges on a specific evaluation approach that adequately gauges the performance for comparative analysis with other researchers' segmentation results. In general, the method performed well and yielded elevated accuracy and efficiency levels in the conducted experiments.
[30]	2021	In this paper, a new segmentation technique has been created and developed	2,500 words of Arabic handwritten samples	The recently employed segmentation algorithm divides the handwritten content into a series of strokes, which are then organized into clusters that showcase the nature of the composed word.
[31]	2022	hybrid approach	KHATT: KFUPM handwritten Arabic text database, and IFN/ENIT	The outcomes of the suggested method demonstrated strong and effective performance in segmenting words. This approach proves to be both efficient and precise for segmenting interconnected and overlapping Arabic characters.
[32]	2021	Projection Profile	Moroccan Quranic manuscript	The results obtained in terms of line segmentation hold promise. However, there were subpar outcomes in character segmentation, stemming from challenges related to complexity.
[33]	2023	Baseline segmentation (BS)	Arabic words from open source	In this paper, baseline segmentation is employed to extract characters from Arabic words. In addition, conventional neural network (CNN) is implemented for classification, and it showed a high accuracy rate compared to other approaches.
[34]	2020	CNN	SUST-ARG: is gathered by the Arabic Recognition Research Group within the School of Computer Science and Information Technology at Sudan University of Science and Technology	The experimental findings indicate that the suggested CNN outperforms other recognition methods when applied to the same dataset. The accuracy achieved for testing names is 99.14%.
[17]	2020	Region-based	Arabic handwritten documents	The proposed method is tested with nine Arabic handwritten images with different style of writing and managed successfully to extract diacritics form these images.

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